

Synthesis and mass spectral studies of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} with 2-hydroxybenzophenone and β -diketones, hydroxyaryl aldehydes or ketones

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Manuscript received 15 January 2007, revised 8 May 2007, accepted 11 June 2007

Abstract : Reactions of cobalt(II) nitrate with two carbonyl compounds (HL and HL') in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios in ethanol have yielded mixed ligand complexes of the type [CoLL'(H₂O)₂] (where HL = 2-hydroxybenzophenone, HL' = salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, TLC, IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, cobalt(II), β -diketones.

We have reported earlier the crystal and molecular structure of 2-hydroxybenzophenone which crystallizes in the space group $P_{21/n}$ and shows intramolecular hydrogen bonding¹. Mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals with 2-hydroxybenzophenone and other carbonyl compounds have also been synthesized and characterized^{1,2}. Octahedral mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} of the type [Co(acac)L(H₂O)₂] (where HL = 8-quinolinol) have been reported³. Mixed ligand complexes of the type [Co(acac)₂L]NO₃ and [Co(acac)₂-L₂]NO₃ (where L = ethylenediamine, propylenediamine, NH₃, 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline) have been studied by Danilczuk⁴. Panda and Mohapatra⁵, have reported octahedral mixed ligand complexes of the type CoL₂L'₂ (where L = *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, L' = quinoline, isoquinoline or morpholine). In the present paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of the mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) of the type [CoLL'(H₂O)₂] (where HL = 2-hydroxybenzophenone (hbpH), HL' = salicylaldehyde (salH), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (hppH), pentane-2,4-dione (acetylacetone, acacH), 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (benzoylacetone, bzacH) or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (dibenzoylmethane, dbzmH).

Results and discussion

Mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} have been synthesized by 1 : 1 : 1 molar reactions of cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate with 2-hydroxybenzophenone and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxypropiophenone.

The mixed ligand complexes with 2-hydroxybenzophenone and β -diketones such as acetylacetone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane have also been synthesized by the similar procedure.

The resulting mixed ligand complexes are brown solids except [Co(hbzp)(dbzm)(H₂O)₂] which is yellow. All the complexes decomposed on heating. They are insoluble in water, benzene and carbon tetrachloride but soluble in DMF. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions in DMF of Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes are in the range 10–35 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggesting them to be non-electrolytes⁶.

TLC of all the mixed ligand complexes was performed on silica gel G using chloroform-petroleum ether (1 : 1) as the solvent. TLC showed single spots having R_f values intermediate of the two corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes. This indicates that they are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes.

Magnetic moments : The μ_{eff} values of the mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} lie in the range 4.05–4.73 B.M. These values are in accordance with the high spin *d*⁷ configuration of Co^{II} suggesting distorted octahedral geometry⁷. Values slightly higher than the spin only value (3.87 B.M.) may be due to orbital contribution^{3,8}.

The IR spectra of Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes exhibit strong absorption bands in the region 1610–1660 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to coordinated ν(C=O). Bands in the region 1525–1555 cm⁻¹ may be due to ν(C=C). In free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylacetone and benzoyl acetone bands at 1680, 1660, 1650, 1724 and 1724 cm⁻¹ respectively have been reported due to ν(C=O)⁹. Thus the shifting of ν(C=O) to lower wave number side in the mixed ligand complexes supports the chelation of these ligands to the metal atom^{5,10}. Weak to medium intensity bands in the region 400–500 cm⁻¹, which are absent in the free ligands may be attributed to ν(Co–O) vibrations. A broad band appears at 3200–3350 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to the coordinated water molecules.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibit bands at ~420 and 530 nm which can be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P)(ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(P)(ν₂) transitions respectively. Bands at 330–380 nm may be due to charge transfer⁷.

FAB mass spectrum of one representative complex [Co(hbp)(bzac)] (**2b**) has been recorded and is reproduced in Fig. 1. The peaks at 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to NBA matrix. The molecular ion (M⁺) peak is observed at *m/z* 417 (22.8%). Peaks at *m/z* 256 (2.8%) and *m/z* 220 (8.5%) are observed due to the species Co(hbp)⁺ and Co(bzac)⁺ respectively, which could have been formed as a result of the loss of either of the two ligand moieties from the molecular ion. In addition to the molecular ion peak due to the mixed ligand complex Co(hbp)(bzac), peaks due to the corresponding bis-complexes Co(hbp)₂⁺ (*m/z* 453, 1.4%) and Co(bzac)₂⁺ (*m/z* 381, 51.4%) are also observed as a result of the redistribution reaction.

A peak at *m/z* 834 (5.7%) is observed due to the dimeric species [Co₂(hbp)₂(bzac)₂]⁺. Loss of one ligand moiety from this dimeric species gives peaks at *m/z* 637 (17.1%) due to [Co₂(hbp)(bzac)₂]⁺ and at *m/z* 673 (2.8%) due to [Co₂(hbp)₂(bzac)]⁺ ions.

Further, there are several peaks in the mass spectrum of the complex which can be assigned to the higher oligomeric species such as Co₂(hbp)₃⁺ (*m/z* 709, 8.6%), Co₂(bzac)₃⁺ (*m/z* 601, 11.4%), Co₂(hbp)₄⁺ (*m/z* 906, 5.7%) and Co(bzac)₄⁺ (*m/z* 762, 11.4%) as reported in case of the mixed ligand complexes of magnesium also¹¹. Thus the FAB mass and other spectral data confirm the proposed structures of the mixed ligand complexes.

Table 1. Analysis and characteristics of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Conductances (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
					C	H	Co		
1.	[Co(hbp)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	210	32	57.80 (58.12)	4.20 (4.39)	14.01 (14.26)	4.32	18
2.	[Co(hbp)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	228	48	58.89 (59.03)	4.54 (4.72)	13.56 (13.79)	4.34	12
3.	[Co(hbp)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	196	45	59.64 (59.87)	4.89 (5.02)	13.61 (13.35)	4.39	35
4.	[Co(hbp)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	254	40	53.65 (53.84)	5.07 (5.31)	15.38 (15.54)	4.20	12
5.	[Co(hbp)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	238	44	60.76 (60.93)	4.76 (4.89)	13.22 (13.00)	4.73	10
6.	[Co(hbp)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	220	50	65.05 (65.25)	4.47 (4.69)	11.28 (11.44)	4.05	15

Table 2. Antibacterial activities of hydroxybenzophenone and Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes

Compd.	Average value of bacteriostatic diameter (mm)		
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>E. aerogenes</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
hbp	6	5	8
[Co(hbp)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	10	9	11
[Co(hbp)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	15	10	12
[Co(hbp)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	11	8	13
[Co(hbp)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6	8	10
[Co(hbp)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	8	7	10
[Co(hbp)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	11	8	14

Biological activities : Antibacterial activities of hydroxybenzophenone and Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes have been determined against bacteria *E. coli*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and are given in Table 2. It is observed that metal chelates have higher activity than the free ligand, which can be explained on the basis of overtone's concept and chelation theory. According to overtone's concept of cell permeability the lipid membrane that surrounds the cell favours the passage of only lipid soluble material. Thus the liposolubility is an important factor that controls the antimicrobial activity. On chelation the polarity of the metal ion is reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of metal ion with donor groups. Further it increases the delocalization of electrons over the whole chelate ring and enhances the lipophilicity of the complex. This increased lipophilicity enhances the penetration of the complexes into the lipid membrane and blocking of metal binding sites on the enzymes of the microorganism.

Experimental

Materials and methods : Cobalt was determined volumetrically by EDTA titration using xylenol orange as indicator¹². Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument. Specific conductances were measured at room temperature in DMF by a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter – 304. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded in the range 300–1100 nm on Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer and FAB mass spectra (*m*-NBA) on a JEOL SX 102 DA-6000 mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Benzoylacetone (SISCO Chem) and dibenzoylmethane (SISCO Chem) were recrystallized from hot ethanol. Salicylaldehyde (Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), 2-hydroxypropiofenone (Fluka), 2-hydroxybenzophenone (Aldrich), acetylacetone (K. Light) and ethanol were purified by distillation. Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Fluka) was of A.R. grade.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) : To a solution of Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (2.04 mmol, 0.595 g in ~10 ml ethanol) an ethanolic solution (~25 ml) of salicylaldehyde (2.04 mmol, 0.249 g) and 2-hydroxybenzophenone (2.04 mmol, 0.405 g) was added with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for about one hour. The pH of the reaction mixture was raised to ~5.5 by adding 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution dropwise with constant stirring. The pH was measured with the help of a pH paper and the stirring was continued for 4–5 h. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similar procedure was followed for the synthesis of other

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of [Co(hbp)(bzac)].

mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} with 2-hydroxybenzophenone and 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione.

Biological activities : Antibacterial activities of the ligand and the complexes have been studied against bacteria *E. coli*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. These were evaluated by the disc diffusion technique using agar nutrient as the medium. Small (8 mm diam.) circular scraps of filter paper were prepared for the purpose of making bacteriostatic slices. 1 % Solutions of the complexes in DMF were used for the studies. A nutrient agar at 45 °C was poured into the petridishes (20–25 ml each) and allowed to solidify. To this, 0.5–0.6 ml of 18–24 h old culture was added and this inoculum was spread evenly by using a spreader. Thereafter, filter paper discs (8 mm) were dipped into the complex solution (10⁻³ M) and were placed on seeded medium. These plates were incubated at 37 °C and extent of inhibition was measured by the zone of inhibition produced after 24 h.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial support, the Head, Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for laboratory facilities, the Head, Chemistry Department, Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali (Rajasthan) for

magnetic measurements and the Director, CDRI, Lucknow for C, H analyses and FAB mass spectra.

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